

ключовий важель розвитку і збереження цивілізації, а швидкість змін перевищила фізіологічні можливості людини, інтерес до «ключових гравців» освітніх інституцій зростає дуже стрімко.

Щодо України, то науковці ХГУ «НУА» вважають: Україна вкотре вже отримала ситуацію нееволюційного розриву розвитку університетських спільнот. Історично схожі ситуації траплялися, як найменше, у 1917, 1937, 1941, 1991 роках. А масштаби втрат, які зазнають університетські спільноти через повномасштабну агресію РФ проти України, виводять питання збереження та відтворення ключових суб'єктів університетського сектору освіти на перші позиції.

Навколо виступів метрів, численних запитань до них, доповнень та ремарок учасників відбулася відверта і професійна дискусія.

Організатори вкотре довели високий фаховий рівень експертного майданчику ХГУ «НУА», якій зібрав зацікавлених учасників, професіоналів найвищого рівня. У відгуках на конференцію, які традиційно зберігаються разом із матеріалами в репозиторії ХГУ «НУА», було відмічено не тільки чітку організацію, високий науковий рівень, а й вплив зустрічі на настрій учасників, на зростання впевненості у перспективах освіти України як рівноправного учасника світового освітнього поля.

Hans de Wit

STRATEGIES TO INTERNATIONALIZE AND EUROPEANIZE HIGHER EDUCATION IN TURBULENT GEOPOLITICAL TIMES

(*Ганс де Віт. Стратегії інтернаціоналізації вищої освіти в турбулентний геополітичний період.*)

The key issues:

What have been and are the main trends, rationales and drivers for internationalization and Europeanization over the past decades?

The different perceptions and meanings of internationalization in and of higher education, and what are key shifting paradigms?

What might be the future directions of internationalization in response to current drastically changing global contexts, with special emphasis on

the future direction of Europeanization: Bologna Process, Erasmus+, Horizon and the European Universities Initiative (EUI). Over the past half century, internationalization in and of higher education has evolved:

– From a marginal and ad hoc range of activities to more comprehensive and central processes and policies. – it has become a key strategic agenda for universities but also national and local governments around the globe. The governments of the Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, India, China, Columbia have their strategies for internationalization.

The context is very important for the process of the internationalization, for example if we take Ukraine and the USA, motives are absolutely different. Different countries have absolutely different approaches to this process. For example my university Boston college, this is a Catholic private university world class rank, a great research center, its motives for internationalization will be absolutely different than in any other educational institution.

– Internationalization is driven by a diverse range of rationales, organizational and program strategies, and includes the involvement of a broad range of stakeholders, internal and external to the system

– But at the same time it has resulted in many different approaches and actions.

– Europe, although confronted with challenges such as Brexit, and it has been leading a regional policy for internationalization with special emphasis on its European dimensions: Europeanization.

Education abroad in all its forms is more driving the agenda than internationalization at home. Increasing focus is made on international rankings.

The divide between the North and the South and between those universities classified as top world-class universities and the “Others” persists.

Internationalization has become more synonym to competition and marketization than to its traditional values (cooperation, exchange and service to society).

Inequality and exclusiveness increased nationally and internationally, in part due to elitist approaches to internationalization.

Recognition of the importance of addressing all aspects of education in an integrated way in university policy and strategy progress is only slowly and unevenly increasing.

A counter reaction: from competition back to cooperation?

As a counter reaction to the exclusive focus on mobility, movements like *'Internationalization at Home'* (Beelen and Jones, 2015), *'Internationalization of the Curriculum'* (Leask, 2015) and *'Comprehensive Internationalization'* (Hudzik, 2015) have emerged around the turn of the century, trying to shift the focus on internationalization for all students, not exclusively the small percentage of mobile ones. Also the rather exclusive focus on only one of the three missions of universities, education, has been challenged with an appeal to more specific attention to *internationalization of research* (Woldegiyorgis et al, 2018) and *internationalization of higher education for society* (Jones et al, 2021).

Looking back to Europeanization.

Over the past 40–50 years the driving rationales for Europeanization in higher education have been competition with the other economic powers (US, Japan-China in particular) and development of a European identity;

Europeanization was in the first place EU, but as of the turn of the century beyond.

Only in 1992 education became a part of the EU competence but with subsidiarity as guiding principle; the examples can be: EU programs for research (framework programs, Horizon) and education (Erasmus+) Bologna Process in 1999, Brexit EUI in 2018.

A multifaceted and evolving concept

Two dimensions, *multifaceted* and *evolving*, are key characteristics of the internationalization of higher education. And one can add, also several of its components such as: study abroad, international students, internationalization at home, transnational or cross-border education, digitalization, the use of terms like 'global citizenship', and so on.

Internationalization is not one model that fits all, its diversity is institutional, local, national and regional defined, and has changed and evolved over time in response to changing contexts and challenges.

A problematic sloppiness, mixing and confusing: the **'why'** (the rationales for internationalization) the **'what'** (its programs and actions), the **'how'** (its organization), the **'impact'** (its outcomes), the **'whom'** (partnerships) and the **'where'** (its context).

In 2003 Knight updated definition and emphasized a *process approach*

involving a wide range of internal (academics, students, administrators) and external (national and local governments, the private sector, international entities) stakeholders.

Knight's definitions of internationalization as a process were an important step forward from the previous use of '*international education*' which was more *ad hoc and fragmented*.

But it still left ample room for different approaches to an understanding of internationalization, including more competitive forms. In that respect, the gradual shift from the term '*international education*' to '*internationalization of higher education*' has not created more clarity about its meaning and focus, reflected also in an *ongoing ad hoc and fragmented reality*.

And it brought *new challenges* to the forefront, as the process involved several *misconceptions* (de Wit, 2011) and *unintended consequences and myths* (Knight, 2009), claiming the need of '*the end of internationalization*' as it was (Brandenburg and de Wit, 2011).

A need for change concerns elitist, competitive and market-oriented approaches to internationalization have persisted.

A need for more attention to the qualitative, human dimensions of internationalization, including global learning for all; employability; improvement of the quality of research, education, and service to society.

Defining Internationalization of Higher Education for the Future reflects increased awareness that

- Mobility must become an integral part of the internationalized curriculum that ensures internationalisation for all.

- Internationalization is not a goal in itself, but a means to enhance quality
- Should not focus solely on economic rationales.

The intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff and to make a meaningful contribution to society. (de Wit et al, 2015, European Parliament Study)

"*This definition gives a normative direction to the process*", distinctive of the more neutral working definition of Knight

Such a more normative approach is also present in other meanings and definitions that have emerged over recent years, such as

‘*Comprehensive internationalization*’ (Hudzik, 2011),

‘*Intelligent internationalization*’ (Rumbley, 2015),

‘*Ethical internationalization*’ (Andreotti, 2016)

‘*Conscientious internationalization*’ (Wolhuter, 2008, Ledger and Kawalilak, 2020)

‘*Responsible internationalization*’ (Stallivieri, 2019) and

‘*Humanistic internationalization*’ (Streitwieser, 2019).

Other definitions have a more focused approach: ‘*learner-centered*’ (Coelen, 2016),

‘*forced*’ (related to refugees, Ergin et al, 2019), and

‘*coerced*’ (Teferra, 2019).

Another term more frequently used these days as alternative to internationalization is ‘*global engagement*’, focusing more on the aspect of cooperation, networking and partnership.

A changing paradigm appeals for change, and a related call for virtual exchange or ‘*Collaborative Online International Learning*’, resonates in words.

In practice the focus continues to be on internationalization abroad, mobility.

De Wit and Rumbley (2017) speak of *rhetoric* more than concrete action, and Leask, Jones and de Wit (2018) of *a struggle to move beyond good intentions and isolated examples of good practice*.

A new generation of scholars, such as those involved in the *Critical Internationalization Studies Network* (CISN, n.d.) is challenging the view of internationalization dominated by Anglo-western perspectives and forms of knowledge.

Jones (2022) argues that “*Equality, diversity and inclusion, social justice, decolonization, global power relations and geopolitics, human rights, anti-racism, gender identity and equality, ethics, multiculturalism, and sustainability are just some of the related elements which all have a role to play in broadening our understanding of internationalization*” (2022: iv).

A changing global landscape implies key challenge geopolitical developments and tensions, increased competition for global talent, health concerns, sustainability/environment, nationalism, racism and other factors.

Key questions, that still remain: how will internationalization be shaped by this global landscape? How will those working in internationalization respond to the challenges they face? And how will they therefore contribute to shaping the future?

Themes for the future are inclusivity and equity, decolonized internationalization, internationalization for society, forced internationalization, internationalization of the curriculum at home, digital internationalization, and the affordability of internationalization.

Decolonizing internationalization reemphasizes the critique of *internationalization as a Western paradigm* (Jones and de Wit, 2014; de Wit, 2020) and the call for '*decolonizing the curriculum*' (Stein, and Andreotti, 2016).

Concerns around the *decolonization and indigenization of curriculum in higher education* are being linked with curriculum internationalization (Buckner & Stein, 2020; Bullen & Flavell, 2021; Leask, 2015; Stein, 2017, 2021; Stein et al., 2020; Stein and Andreotti, 2016).

Implications for Europe and Ukraine broaden its scope;

Taking into account guiding other regional initiatives (ASEAN);

Stronger focus is made on Africa;

EUI lay between stability and growth, between bureaucratic constraints and high ambitions;

We try to solve the negative consequences of Brexit, but mainly in research.

Solidarity as the key component of our future research.

Philip Altbach

GLOBAL TRENDS IN HIGHER EDUCATION: UNDERLYING REALITIES AND CURRENT CRISES

(Філіп Альтбах. Глобальні тенденції у сфері вищої освіти: сучасні реалії та кризи.)

The purpose of this discussion is large – to place global higher education in the context of the significant changes of the early 21st century, to highlight some of the key crisis points of today's complex environment, and to relate these realities to internationalization